

Gender STI

D1.2 - Survey Report on Gender Equality Implementation in STI Bilateral and Multilateral Agreements.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report (Deliverable D1.2) presents the results of the survey carried out by the Gender STI project in order to investigate the status of the implementation of gender equality in STI bilateral and multilateral agreements between European Member States (MS) and Associated countries (AC) on one side, and third countries on the other side.

In particular, the survey aimed to learn more about the state of gender equality in STI bilateral and multilateral agreements in the project's three focus areas: gender equality in scientific careers; gender equality in decision-making bodies and positions; and the integration of the gender dimension in research and innovation (R&I) content.

D1.2 is organized as follows:

- Section 1 introduces the objectives and scope of the survey to analyse gender equality in bilateral and multilateral agreements in science, technology and innovation (STI).
- Section 2 discusses the methodology used to carry out the survey, detailing aspects such as scope and sample size, the online questionnaire, privacy measures taken to adhere to General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR) and communication actions taken to promote the survey.
- Section 3 details the survey's results, including aspects such as respondent gender, respondent regional classification, respondent organization type and respondent position. It then dives into the analysis of specific questions related to the gender perspective in STI agreements, gender equality in scientific careers, gender equality in decision-making bodies and positions, the integration of the gender perspective in research and innovation content and motivations and barriers preventing the inclusion of gender equality in STI agreements.

This section also includes insights from survey respondents, who discussed gender equality and the survey at length in voluntary comments.

- Section 4 presents our conclusion.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Gender STI survey aims to assess the current state of gender equality in international cooperation in science, technology and innovation (STI). The survey analyses gender equality in bilateral and multilateral agreements (formal and/or informal) between European Member States, Associated Countries and selected third countries. These include bilateral agreements, multilateral agreements, memorandums of understanding and STI implementation activities, such as calls for proposals, rules for participation and evaluation criteria.

Unfortunately, not much is known about whether these international agreements include gender equality when they are being negotiated. This lack of knowledge does not create an environment where advancements in gender equality can be made, as no change can be made without having a full picture of the current state of the matter.

In this context the Gender STI project, which is composed of 18 organizations across 4 continents, launched an international survey on the subject. In order to gain more insight on whether gender equality was being considered in the bilateral and multilateral agreements between Europe and 10 selected third countries (Canada, the US, Mexico, Brazil, Chile, Argentina, South Africa, India, South Korea and China). Specifically, the survey seeks to collect valuable input on key measures to implement gender equality in STI across the three objectives pursued by EU gender equality strategy in R&I: gender equality in scientific careers, gender balance in decision-making bodies and the gender dimension in research and innovation content.

The survey also attempts to identify the main barriers or reasons that prevent the inclusion of gender equality in STI bilateral and multilateral agreements.

Considering the impact science has had in our lives since the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic—and the role women have played in achieving key scientific breakthroughs—it is now clearer than ever that gender equality in STI is a priority that must be pursued.

International bilateral and multilateral agreements that take into account gender equality play an important role in this regard, as they can foster the inclusion of women in important research worldwide, help create long-term career pathways for them, encourage women to take on leadership positions, and spur research questions on the gender dimension in R&I content.

2 SURVEY METHODOLOGY

2.1 Scope and Sample Size

The “Survey on Gender Equality in STI Bilateral and Multilateral Agreements” was sent to a sample size of roughly 1,450 key actors from MS, AC and third countries participating in the project, including members of government organizations, funding organizations, Research and Technology Organizations (RTOs), universities, foundations, private companies, public companies, STI agencies and associations and NGOs. A full breakdown of respondents is presented in section 3.1.

The survey was open from June to September 2021 and received 204 responses with a response rate of 14%. However, since some questions were conditional, not all of them required a response. Others were multiple choice questions. Therefore, not all questions included answers as they were optional to respond.

Each partner in the Gender STI consortium—consisting of 18 well-established organizations in 16 countries, of which 6 are EU MS and 10 are third countries—invited a selected number of key actors and follow-up closely until reaching between 10-20 stakeholders in their home countries to complete the survey and share their perspective on the subject matter.

2.2 Online Questionnaire

The survey included 17 questions presented in open ended, multiple choice and ranking formats (see Annex 1).

It asked participants about the gender perspective in STI agreements, gender equality implementation in STI, motivations and barriers, measures to advance the integration of the gender perspective in STI and recommendations to improve international cooperation in STI.

The questionnaire was carried out on the online survey platform, Survey Monkey¹. This tool was chosen because it is easy to use for respondents, fast to collect responses and convenient to analyse the results. It has been proven to offer an optimized process of distribution, response collection and visualization of data analysis.

To protect data privacy, follow General Data Protection Regulations and ensure response anonymity, the following actions were carried out:

- For the GDPR reasons, the individual lists of stakeholders invited to take the survey were not circulated among partner organizations. Partner INMARK was responsible of the survey administration and data analysis. In addition, potentially identifiable response data, e.g., email addresses, were not shared with the consortium.
- Respondents were not asked to provide their name or their specific affiliation. Only general demographic questions were asked. Respondents could voluntarily provide their email address if they wished to receive a copy of the survey report.
- There was only one administrator that could access the completed questionnaires.

¹ About Us: We Power the Curious. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://www.surveymonkey.com/mp/aboutus/>

- Backups of responses obtained were performed every week to avoid accidental deletion of the data.
- INMARK enabled two-factor authentication for the project's Survey Monkey account to ensure respondent data was secure.

In addition, a privacy statement was included before the survey began.

Figure 1: Survey Privacy Statement

The text of the statement was as follows:

"Please note that your responses will be kept absolutely confidential and will not be disclosed to any third parties. Data will be used in aggregated form only and individual comments will not be attributed to their originators. Participation in this survey is voluntary. You may leave the survey at any time."

2.3 Communication Actions to Promote the Survey

As an official Gender STI activity, promotion of the survey was part of the project's Communication and Dissemination plan. We also carried out actions on the Gender STI website, social media and through email campaigns.

Examples of the survey blog post, social media posts and the template used for the email campaign can be found in Annex 2.

Survey Promotional Image

The survey's promotional image was designed in a simple style to ensure the survey's topic stood out to users. It aimed to convey a message of gender equality by making the Greek symbols for woman ("♀") and man ("♂") the primary design elements. In addition, the image elegantly references science by including the fading molecules on the left and right sides. All of these elements are brought together using Gender STI's brand colors—purple, white and blue—and logo, thereby identifying the activity as a project activity.

Survey Blog

To communicate the launch of the survey, we developed a blog post featuring the promotional image above and posted it on the project's website and social media channels. The blog was written in an easy-to-understand style and optimized according to SEO best practices (e.g., concise SEO title, meta description and links to third-party authoritative sources).

The blog's purpose was twofold. On one hand, it aimed to create buzz about the survey and increase the survey's sample size. On the other hand, the blog also explained the survey's research purpose and goals and was used as a reference article by partners who invited high-level stakeholders to complete the questionnaire. In the latter scenario, sometimes stakeholders wanted more information about the survey before they decided to participate. In those cases, consortium partners would send stakeholders a link to the blog.

Survey Social Media Posts

We promoted the survey on the project's three social media channels: [Twitter](#), [LinkedIn](#) and [Facebook](#). Like the blog post on the project's website, social media posts aimed to drum up interest in the survey. Although the survey invitation list was determined by each consortium member—only consortium members could send invitations—the social media posts also provided anyone interested in participating in the survey the opportunity to get in touch via email.

Survey Email Campaign

We launched a series of 8 email campaigns to 601 users inviting them to learn more about and participate in the survey. Each campaign was personalized according to

the stakeholder groups' profile in order to increase the probability that they would decide to take the survey.

Invitation to Sister Projects

In addition, we also reached out to 20 sister projects financed by the Horizon 2020 framework program focusing on gender equality and related topics, such as gender equality plans, gender budgeting and communities of practice, among others. We invite the sister projects to participate in the survey and received a positive response from many of them.

3 SURVEY RESULTS

3.1 Profile of Survey Respondents

In order to achieve a balanced view of the current state of gender equality in STI bilateral and multilateral agreements, the consortium aimed to obtain approximately 50% of answers from Europe and 50% of answers from selected third countries. A total of 98 (48.03%) stakeholders from Europe completed the survey. When it comes to third countries, 106 stakeholders (51.96%) from the 10 countries represented in the consortium completed the survey.

Figure 2: Survey Respondents by Region

Gender

Although the survey was sent to a series of stakeholders, both women and men, who actively work in gender equality, the majority of our respondents (76.47%) were women. This could be an indication that women are the ones leading the campaigns for gender equality in their organizations. Men represented 22.55% and nonbinary people represented 0.98%, respectively.

Nonetheless, the disproportionate number of responses from women does not detract from the survey findings and is beneficial to this survey. Gender barriers in STI are experienced by women more often than men and the focus of this work is barriers that women experience. The large proportion of responses from women help us to understand the issues, barriers and potential approaches to them that are most important to women.

Figure 3: Survey Respondents by Gender

Organization Type

The survey received the most responses (55%) from participants who work at universities (37.35%) and research and technology organizations, or RTOs, (17.65%), followed by government organizations (28.43%). Overall, responses from academia and civil servants made up 83.43% of respondents.

Figure 4: Survey Respondents by Organization Type

Position at Organizations

Survey respondents classified themselves as either director (18.72%), government official/civil servant (14.29%) or project manager (14.29%). When it comes to the “other” category (15.76%), we received a range of responses, including diplomats, founders, COOs, and members of equality units, among many others.

Figure 5: Survey Respondents by Position

3.2 Gender Perspective in Science, Technology and Innovation (STI) Agreements

3.2.1 STI Cooperation Agreements with Other Countries

To start off the survey, we asked participants about STI cooperation agreements their organizations had formed with other countries. We felt that this was key as it gave us a sense of understanding of the reach of the agreements and the awareness around them.

A majority of respondents (66.50%) said their organizations had formed agreements. 18.23% said they had not, while 15.27% said they didn't know.

Figure 6: Organizations That Have Established STI Agreements With Other Countries

3.2.2 Gender-Related Provisions in Ongoing STI Cooperation Agreements

After introducing the concept of STI cooperation agreements, we focused on the next critical part of our survey: the inclusion of gender-related provisions in these agreements. Since STI cooperation agreements can take many forms, we included the most common types of agreements in this question: bilateral agreements, multilateral agreements, bilateral memorandums of understanding, multilateral memorandums of understanding and STI implementation activities.

Figure 7: Organizations That Have Included Gender-Related Provisions in STI Agreements

For almost every type of agreement, roughly a third part of respondents declared that they “didn’t know” whether their organizations had included gender-related provisions in ongoing STI cooperation agreements. Nonetheless, it should be noted that more than 20% of respondents said their organization “sometimes” included gender-related provisions in STI cooperation agreements.

The exception was STI implementation activities, where 19.07% of respondents said their organization “always” included gender-related provisions in this type of agreement, while 35.05% said their organizations “sometimes” did so. This suggests that gender-related provisions are being included in the updates of the agreements through implementation activities.

Table 1: Organizations That Include Gender-Related Provisions in Ongoing STI Cooperation Agreements

Type of Agreement	Always	Sometimes	Never	I Don't Know	N/A	Total
Bilateral Agreement	7.22%	25.77%	25.26%	30.41%	11.34%	100% (194)
Multilateral Agreement	7.41%	24.34%	22.22%	31.75%	14.29%	100% (189)
Bilateral Memorandum of Understanding (MoU)	6.77%	21.88%	24.48%	33.85%	13.02%	100% (192)
Multilateral Memorandum of Understanding (MoU)	7.33%	20.42%	23.04%	36.13%	13.09%	100% (191)
STI implementation activities (e.g., call for proposals, rules for participation, evaluation criteria, etc.)	19.07%	35.05%	16.49%	20.62%	8.76%	100% (194)

As far as what areas of gender-related provisions are addressed in STI cooperation agreements, the top three responses were the following: “Contribution to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)” (24.46%), “STI objectives/priorities” (22.34%) and “Calls for proposals/applications” (21.28%).

A second group of areas addressing gender equality (around 19% of responses) include: evaluation criteria for STI programs/projects; gender dimension in research content; science communication; agreements advice/recommendations on implementing gender equality; and rules for participation.

Figure 8: Areas of Gender-Related Provisions Addressed in STI Cooperation Agreements

You can see the full breakdown in the table below.

Table 2: Areas of Gender-Related Provisions Addressed in STI Cooperation Agreements

Areas	Always	Sometimes	Never	I Don't Know	N/A	Total
Agreements advice/recommendations on implementing gender equality	19.02%	34.78%	10.33%	20.65%	15.22%	100% (184)
STI objectives/priorities (e.g., strengthen research excellence, increase the number of women researchers in STI activities, etc.)	22.34%	34.04%	9.04%	20.21%	14.36%	100% (188)
Evaluation criteria for STI programs/projects	19.25%	28.34%	12.83%	23.53%	16.04%	100% (187)
Monitoring of STI programs/projects	15.08%	24.58%	16.2%	26.82%	17.32%	100% (179)
Calls for proposals/applications	21.28%	36.7%	11.17%	18.09%	12.77%	100% (188)
Rules for participation	18.92%	27.57%	14.05%	23.78%	15.68%	100% (185)
Impact of project results	15%	31.67%	12.22%	25%	16.11%	100% (180)
Science communication	19.13%	28.96%	11.48%	26.78%	13.66%	100% (183)
Contribution to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)	24.46%	31.52%	8.15%	20.65%	15.22%	100% (184)
Gender dimension in research content	19.13%	37.16%	8.2%	21.86%	13.66%	100% (183)

Findings on the Inclusion of Gender-Related Provisions and Areas Addressed in STI Cooperation Agreements

- Respondents from Europe and Third Countries overall don't seem to know whether their organizations include gender-related provisions in ongoing STI cooperation agreements, strictly speaking, with other countries.
- However, respondents from both groups seem to be more aware of the gender-related provisions in STI implementation activities, with 54.12% saying that their organization "always" or "sometimes" included gender-related provisions in this area.
- Nonetheless, respondents from both groups indicated that the gender-related provisions most often included in STI agreements refer to the following areas: Contribution to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (24.46%), STI objectives/priorities (22.34%) and calls for proposals/applications (21.28%).

3.2.3 Gender Equality When Renewing or Establishing STI Cooperation Agreements

We found parallels when we asked respondents whether they knew if their organizations considered addressing gender equality when they renewed or established new STI agreements with other countries. As with the question regarding gender-related provisions, roughly a third of participants responded that they "didn't know" whether their organization considered this for almost every type of agreements (bilateral agreements, multilateral agreements, bilateral memorandum of understanding, and multilateral memorandum of understanding).

Nonetheless, 50.78% of respondents said their organizations "always" or "sometimes" considered addressing gender equality in new bilateral agreements. In the case of STI implementation activities, this percentage is close to 60%, which suggests that gender equality is being implemented in practice through call for proposals, rules for participation, evaluation criteria, among other.

Table 3: Gender Equality When Renewing Current or Establishing New STI Agreements

Type of Agreement	Always	Sometimes	Never	I Don't Know	N/A	Total
Bilateral Agreement	20.94%	29.84%	9.95%	30.37%	8.9%	100% (191)
Multilateral Agreement	21.05%	26.32%	8.42%	33.68%	10.53%	100% (190)
Bilateral Memorandum of Understanding (MoU)	20.74%	26.06%	10.64%	31.91%	10.64%	100% (188)
Multilateral Memorandum of Understanding (MoU)	18.62%	26.06%	9.04%	34.57%	11.7%	100% (188)
STI implementation activities (e.g., call for proposals, rules for participation, evaluation criteria, etc.)	25.65%	34.03%	6.81%	25.65%	7.85%	100% (191)

For those participants whose organizations considered addressing gender equality in the renewal or establishment of new STI agreements, we asked them to provide additional insight on what areas gender equality aspects would be included.

The three most popular areas to address gender equality were: "Advice/recommendations on implementing gender equality" (32.4%), "STI objectives/priorities" (29.0%) and "Calls for proposals/applications" (28.8%), and "Calls for proposals/applications" (21.28%). As in ongoing STI Cooperation Agreements, gender equality in calls for proposals and applications is considered a critical issue.

A second group of areas to address gender equality in new STI agreements (more than 27% responses) include: "Contribution to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)", "Evaluation criteria for STI programs/projects", and "gender dimension in research content".

Figure 9: Areas to Address Gender Equality in New STI Agreements

You can check out the full breakdown in the table below.

Table 4: Areas Where Gender Equality Will Be Considered When Renewing or Establishing STI Agreements

Areas	Always	Sometimes	Never	I Don't Know	N/A	Total
Agreements advice/recommendations on implementing gender equality	32.42%	25.82%	3.3%	26.37%	12.09%	100% (182)
STI objectives/priorities (e.g., strengthen research excellence, increase the number of women researchers in STI activities, etc.)	28.96%	30.05%	2.19%	26.78%	12.02%	100% (183)
Evaluation criteria for STI programs/projects	27.62%	26.52%	4.97%	28.73%	12.15%	100% (181)
Monitoring of STI programs/projects	23.73%	24.86%	4.52%	32.2%	14.69%	100% (177)
Calls for proposals/applications	28.8%	33.15%	3.8%	22.28%	11.96%	100% (184)
Rules for participation	26.26%	29.05%	5.59%	27.37%	11.73%	100% (179)
Impact of project results	19.54%	34.48%	3.45%	28.74%	13.79%	100% (174)

Areas	Always	Sometimes	Never	I Don't Know	N/A	Total
Science communication	23.63%	30.22%	5.49%	27.47%	13.19%	100% (182)
Contribution to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)	27.78%	30%	2.78%	26.11%	13.33%	100% (180)
Gender dimension in research content	27.12%	30.51%	4.52%	25.42%	12.43%	100% (177)

Breakdown Between Europe and Third Countries

For this question, which asked about areas where gender equality will be considered when renewing or establishing new STI agreements, respondents from Europe and Third Countries in general coincided in their responses. Because this question used a Likert-type scale response system to measure frequency, we created a classification system based on the data we received. In this case, similarities are defined as answers that are within 1 to 14.90 percentage points of each other. Close similarities are defined as answers that are within less than 1 percentage points of each other. Meanwhile, we define a difference as a divergence of at least 15 percentage points between answers.

Similarities

There were more similarities than differences in all areas, although responses seem to suggest that participants from Third Countries are more aware of the content areas for gender equality in STI agreements based on the amount of “I don’t know” responses from Europe (the most selected answer in all categories). In comparison, “I don’t know” was never the most selected answer in any category for respondents from Third Countries.

There were similarities between both groups in 7 of the 10 areas analyzed in which gender equality was always considered in the renewal or establishment of new STI agreements. The areas are the following: “STI objectives/priorities”; “Evaluation criteria for STI programs/projects”; “Calls for proposals/applications”; “Rules for participation”; “Science communication”; “Contribution to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)”; and “Gender dimension in research content”.

Notably, when it comes to “Impact of project results,” 34.18% of Europeans and 34.74% of people from Third Countries said that this area was “sometimes” considered when renewing or establishing STI agreements. This is a difference of 0.56%, which means we can infer that the “Impact of project results” is considered in the scope of gender equality when renewing or establishing STI agreements.

Differences

When comparing responses from survey participants from Europe and Third Countries, a notable takeaway—which we define as a difference of at least 15 percentage points between answers—was the amount of “I don’t know” responses received from Europe.

Europeans indicated that they didn’t know whether gender equality was considered when renewing or establishing STI agreements for all areas analyzed. Interestingly, “I don’t know” was also the most popular answer choice among European respondents for all areas analyzed (between 32.53% and 44.87% of responses).

Nonetheless, there were also differences in between Europe and Third Countries in other areas. For instance, 40% of respondents from Third Countries indicated that

“Advice/recommendations on implementing gender equality” were “always” considered when renewing or establishing new STI agreements compared to 23.17% of respondents from Europe, a difference of 16.83 points.

Practically double number of respondents from Third Countries (30.30% compared to 15.38% from Europe) were also more likely to say that “Monitoring of STI programs/projects” were “always” considered in new STI agreements.

There were also differences when it comes to the “Impact of project results,” with 26.32% of respondents from Third Countries indicating that this was “always” considered when renewing or establishing agreements. In comparison, 11.39% of Europeans said this was “always” considered, a difference of 14.93 points.

Table 5: Side by Side Comparison of Areas Where Gender Equality Will Be Considered When Renewing or Establishing STI Agreements: Europe and Third Countries

Areas		Always	Sometimes	Never	I Don't Know	N/A	Total
Europe	Agreements advice/recommendations on implementing gender equality	23.17%	24.39%	3.66%	37.8%	10.98%	95.35% (82/86)
Third Countries		40%	27%	3%	17%	13%	96.51% (83/86)
Europe	STI objectives/priorities (e.g., strengthen research excellence, increase the number of women researchers in STI activities, etc.)	21.69%	27.71%	2.41%	38.55%	9.64%	96.51% (83/86)
Third Countries		35%	32%	2%	17%	14%	97.09% (100/103)
Europe	Evaluation criteria for STI programs/projects	19.75%	25.93%	3.7%	41.98%	8.64%	94.19% (81/86)
Third Countries		34%	27%	6%	18%	15%	97.09% (100/103)
Europe	Monitoring of STI programs/projects	15.38%	23.08%	3.85%	44.87%	12.82%	90.7% (78/86)
Third Countries		30.3%	26.26%	5.05%	22.22%	16.16%	96.12% (99/103)
Europe	Calls for proposals/applications	24.1%	31.33%	3.61%	32.53%	8.43%	96.51% (83/86)
Third Countries		32.67%	34.65%	3.96%	13.86%	14.85%	98.06% (101/103)
Europe	Rules for participation	21.25%	25%	6.25%	40%	7.5%	93.02% (80/86)
Third Countries		30.3%	32.32%	5.05%	17.17%	15.15%	96.12% (99/103)
Europe	Impact of project results	11.39%	34.18%	3.8%	39.24%	11.39%	91.86% (79/86)
Third Countries		26.32%	34.74%	3.16%	20%	15.79%	92.23% (95/103)
Europe	Science communication	18.29%	26.83%	4.88%	39.02%	10.98%	95.35% (82/86)
Third Countries		28%	33%	6%	18%	15%	97.09% (100/103)
Europe	Contribution to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)	25.3%	24.1%	3.61%	38.55%	8.43%	96.51% (83/86)
Third Countries		29.9%	35.05%	2.06%	15.46%	17.53%	94.17% (97/103)
Europe	Gender dimension in research content	20.99%	27.16%	3.7%	38.27%	9.88%	94.19% (81/86)

Areas	Always	Sometimes	Never	I Don't Know	N/A	Total
Third Countries	32.29%	33.33%	5.21%	14.58%	14.58%	93.2% (96/103)

Findings on Gender Equality When Renewing or Establishing STI Agreements

- Overall, roughly a third of participants responded that they "didn't know" whether their organization considered gender equality when renewing or establishing STI agreements.
- Participants whose organizations were considering gender equality when renewing or establishing STI agreements indicated that the most popular areas to address gender equality were: Advice/recommendations on implementing gender equality (32.42%), STI objectives/priorities (28.96%) and Calls for proposals/applications (28.89%).
- When broken out for comparison, responses from Europe and Third Countries seem to suggest that participants from Third Countries are more aware of the content areas for gender equality in STI agreements.
- Respondents from Europe (34.18%) and Third Countries (34.74%) indicated that Impact of project results is considered in the scope of gender equality when renewing or establishing STI agreements.

3.3 Gender Equality Implementation in STI

The survey also inquired about gender equality implementation in three focus areas, i.e., gender equality in scientific careers at all levels; gender balance in decision-making bodies and positions in STI; and gender dimension in research and innovation content. Respondents were asked to select the three most important issues for achieving gender equality in these areas. Nonetheless, rankings were not weighed. Therefore, the most popular issues as selected by respondents are considered the *most* important.

3.3.1 Gender Equality in Scientific Careers

The three most popular approaches to improve gender equality in STI when it comes to scientific careers at all levels were: gender equality in recruitment and career progression (74.51%); parental leave policies/flexible work schedule arrangements (35.78%); and incentives for women to lead projects (33.33%).

Figure 10: Approaches to Improve Gender Equality in STI in Scientific Careers at All Levels

Breakdown Between Europe and Third Countries

When comparing the ranking from European and Third Countries participants we found that although respondents coincided on what they considered the most important approach to improve gender equality in STI in scientific careers—i.e., gender equality in recruitment and career progression—they differed slightly in their following choices and the importance of those choices.

Similarities

Interestingly, 73.47% of participants from Europe and 73.47% of participants from Third Countries ranked “Gender equality in recruitment and career progression” as one of the most important approaches to improve gender equality in scientific careers, making it the most selected answer.

There were also similarities for the third most selected approach for Europe and Third Countries. Both ranked “Visibility to women references in science” as an important approach. In the case of Europe this approach was selected by 31.63% of respondents. Meanwhile, respondents from Third Countries overall chose, “Visibility to women references in science,” which was tied with “Unconscious bias training for the scientific community” at 31.13%.

Differences

Respondents from Europe and Third Countries did differ on the second most selected approach. At 44.90%, Europeans considered “Parental leave policies/flexible work schedule arrangements” to be an important approach. However, only 28.30% of respondents from Third Countries considered this approach important, making it the fourth most selected option.

As the second most selected approach, respondents from Third Countries chose “Incentives for women to lead projects,” which received 41.51% of responses.

Table 6: Side by Side Comparison of Approaches to Improve Gender Equality in Scientific Careers: Europe and Third Countries

Approaches	Total	Europe	Third Countries
Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	74,51%	73.47%	75.47%
Inclusive language for job vacancies	8,33%	14.29%	2.83%
Parental leave policies/flexible work schedule arrangements	35,78%	44.90%	28.3%
Job security for women in the long-term	20,59%	20.41%	20.75%
Visibility to women references in science	31,37%	31.63%	31.13%
Training on equitable hiring practices	13,73%	8.16%	18.87%
Mentorship of women by other women	12,25%	13.27%	11.32%
Incentives for women to lead projects	33,33%	24.49%	41.51%
Gender balanced peer reviews	20,59%	16.33%	24.53%
Retaining women scientists	16,18%	20.41%	12.26%
Unconscious bias training for the scientific community	30,88%	30.61%	31.13%
Other	1,96%	2.04%	1.89%
Total	100% (204)	100% (98)	100% (106)

Results for Europe and Third Countries related to improving gender equality in scientific careers are presented in a series of graphs in Annex 3.

Findings on Gender Equality in Scientific Careers

- To achieve gender equality in scientific careers, respondents from both groups considered the following three approaches to be the most important: gender equality in recruitment and career progression (74.51%); parental leave policies/flexible work schedule arrangements (35.78%); and incentives for women to lead projects (33.33%).
- When comparing responses from Europe and Third Countries, we found that they mostly coincided when determining the most important approaches to achieve gender equality in scientific careers.
- Nonetheless, respondents from these groups did differ on one approach. 44.90% of Europeans considered "Parental leave policies/flexible work schedule arrangements" to be an important approach, making it the second most selected approach. Only 28.30% of respondents from Third Countries considered this approach important, which made this approach the fourth most selected for this group.

In turn, 41.51% respondents from Third Countries chose "Incentives for women to lead projects." It was the second most selected approach for this group.

3.3.2 Gender Balance in Decision-Making Bodies and Positions

We also asked participants to identify and rank what issues need to be addressed to improve the gender balance in decision-making bodies and positions in STI, which is another one of the project's focus areas.

Overall, respondents said the three most important issues to address were “Policies to increase the proportion of women in STI (52.94%)”, “Participation of women in the negotiation of STI agreements” (50.49%) and “Gender balance in STI policy dialogues” (45.10%). The range across all responses doesn’t seem very large. That tells us that there are a lot of issues to be addressed across all of the areas of improvement of gender balance in decision-making bodies and positions in STI.

Figure 11: Improve the Gender Balance in Decision-Making Bodies and Positions in STI

Breakdown Between Europe and Third Countries

As this was also a ranking question, we will present an analysis of the three most popular answers from European and Third Countries participants.

Similarities

The majority of respondents from Europe (52.04%) and Third Countries (53.77%) considered that “Policies to increase the proportion of women in STI” was an important issue that needed to be addressed to improve the gender balance in decision-making bodies and positions. When it comes to participants from Third Countries, however, there was a tie: Respondents considered the “Participation of women in the negotiation of STI agreements” to be an equally important issue (53.77%).

Differences

As far as differences go, European respondents considered “Ensuring transparent nomination and promotion schemes in political and corporate cultures” (50%) and

“Participation of women in the negotiation of STI agreements” (46.94%) important issues. These answers were the second and third most selected issues, respectively. However, the differences are small and there is less than 15 percentage points of difference for all answers.

Participants from Third Countries didn’t coincide in either ranking. They considered “Gender balance in STI policy dialogues” (48.11%) and “Introducing gender quotas for evaluation panels to ensure a gender-balanced composition” (37.74%) to be important issues, with the former being the second most popular answer and the latter being the third most popular answer.

Table 7: Side by Side Comparison of Issues to Improve the Gender Balance in Decision-Making Bodies and Positions: Europe and Third Countries

Issues	Total	Europe	Third Countries
Gender balance in STI policy dialogues	45,10%	41.84%	48.11%
Participation of women in the negotiation of STI agreements	50,49%	46.94%	53.77%
Introducing gender quotas for evaluation panels to ensure a gender-balanced composition	37,75%	37.76%	37.74%
Disseminating updated information, trends and good practices on gender equality in decision-making	32,35%	28.57%	36.79%
Policies to increase the proportion of women in STI	52,94%	52.04%	53.77%
Ensuring transparent nomination and promotion schemes in political and corporate cultures	40,69%	50.00%	32.08%
Unconscious bias training on gender balance in leadership positions	37,75%	40.82%	34.91%
Other	2,45%	2.04%	2.83%
Total	100% (204)	100% (98)	100% (106)

Results for Europe and Third Countries related to improving the gender balance in decision-making bodies and positions are presented in a series of graphs in Annex 4.

Findings on Improving the Gender Balance in Decision-Making Bodies and Positions in STI

- Overall, respondents said the three most important issues to address were: “Policies to increase the proportion of women in STI (52.94%)”; “Participation of women in the negotiation of STI agreements” (50.49%); and “Gender balance in STI policy dialogues” (45.10%).
- When breaking out responses from Europe and Third Countries, respondents from both groups highlighted “Policies to increase the proportion of women in STI,” which was the most selected option by both groups.
- Both groups did not coincide on the second and third most selected option, however.

European respondents considered “Ensuring transparent nomination and promotion schemes in political and corporate cultures” (50%) and “Participation of women in the negotiation of STI agreements” (46.94%) important issues. Participants from Third Countries, meanwhile, considered “Gender balance in STI policy dialogues” (48.11%) and “Introducing gender quotas for evaluation panels to ensure a gender-balanced composition” (37.74%) to be important issues.

3.3.3 Gender Dimension in Research and Innovation Content

Lastly, we asked participants to share their views on what they believe needs to be addressed to integrate the gender dimension in research and innovation content, Gender STI's third focus area.

Figure 12: Integrating the Gender Dimension in Research and Innovation Content

The three most popular answers were: "Consider gender in the entire research and innovation process" (77.45%); "Create criteria to monitor the gender dimension in research content, processes and outcomes" (63.73%); and "Ensure gender balance in research teams" (46.57%).

Breakdown Between Europe and Third Countries

When comparing the ranking from European and Third Countries participants regarding the integration of the gender dimension in research and innovation content, there are more similarities than differences.

Similarities

The great majority of respondents from Europe and Third Countries coincided on the most important and second most important issues that need to be addressed to integrate the gender dimension in research and innovation content. "Consider gender in the entire research and innovation process" was the most selected answer, with 79.59% of European respondents and 75.47% of respondents from Third Countries choosing it.

Meanwhile, "Create criteria to monitor the gender dimension in research content, processes and outcomes" ended up as the second most popular answer and was chosen by 63.27% of respondents from Europe and 64.15% of respondents from Third Countries.

Differences

The groups differed on the third most popular answer. 48.98% Europeans considered “Address gender bias in research design” to be one of the most important issues, while 52.83% of respondents from Third Countries considered that “Ensure gender balance in in research teams” was one of the most important issues.

Table 8: Side by Side Comparison of Issues to be Addressed to Integrate the Gender Dimension in Research and Innovation Content: Europe and Third Countries

Issues	Total	Europe	Third Countries
Consider gender in the entire research and innovation process	77,45%	79.59%	75.47%
Address gender bias in research design	41,18%	48.98%	34.91%
Ensure gender balance in evaluation panels	43,14%	35.71%	50.94%
Ensure gender balance in research teams	46,57%	39.8%	52.83%
Include gender factors in application forms	23,53%	28.57%	18.87%
Create criteria to monitor the gender dimension in research content, processes and outcomes	63,73%	63.27%	64.15%
Other	3,43%	4.08%	2.83%
Total	100% (204)	100% (98)	100% (106)

Results for Europe and Third Countries related to integrating the gender dimension are presented in a series of graphs in Annex 5.

Findings on Integrating the Gender Dimension in R&I Content

- Overall, respondents said the following needs to be addressed in order to integrate the gender dimension in R&I content: “Consider gender in the entire research and innovation process” (77.45%); “Create criteria to monitor the gender dimension in research content, processes and outcomes” (63.73%); and “Ensure gender balance in research teams” (46.57%).
- When breaking out responses by groups, Europeans and respondents from Third Countries coincided on the first and second most popular answers: “Consider gender in the entire research and innovation process” and “Create criteria to monitor the gender dimension in research content, processes and outcomes”.
- They differed on the third most selected issue. While 48.98% of Europeans considered “Address gender bias in research design” to be one of the most important issues, the majority of respondents from Third Countries (52.83%) give more relevance to “Ensure gender balance in research teams”.

3.4 Motivations and Barriers

3.4.1 Motivations

We also felt that the survey needed to pinpoint why respondents feel the gender perspective should be considered in STI bilateral and multilateral agreements. Respondents were asked to provide the three most important reasons to consider the gender perspective. Nonetheless, rankings were not weighed, and respondents were

asked to select those they deemed most important. Therefore, the most popular responses as selected by respondents are considered the *most* important.

The three most important reasons to include the gender perspective in STI bilateral and multilateral agreements were the following: to further the inclusion of the gender dimension in research and innovation programs (50%); economic benefits and the availability of the best human capital (43.63%); and increased awareness of the benefits of gender sensitive and responsive research (42.65%).

Figure 13: Motivations Why the Gender Perspective Should Be Included in STI Bilateral and Multilateral Agreements

Breakdown Between Europe and Third Countries

As this was a ranking question, we will present an analysis of the three most popular answers from European and Third Countries participants. In this case, there weren't that many differences between respondents.

Similarities

The most selected reason why the gender perspective should be included in STI bilateral and multilateral agreements was "To further the inclusion of the gender dimension in research and innovation programs." 47.96% of European respondents selected this answer, compared to 51.89% of respondents from Third Countries.

Respondents from both groups also selected "Economic benefits and the availability of the best human capital" as an important reason why the gender perspective should be included in the agreements. It was the third most popular reason selected by both groups. 43.88% of respondents from Europe considered this reason to be important, Meanwhile, 45.28% of respondents from Third Countries considered this reason to be important.

Differences

Nonetheless, respondents from both groups differed on the second most selected reason. 46.94% of Europeans stated that “Increased awareness of the benefits of gender sensitive and responsive research” was an important reason. On the other side, 45.28% of respondents from Third Countries considered “Gender diversity is a top priority in the global research landscape” to be important.

Table 9: Side by Side Comparison of Why the Gender Perspective Should Be Included in STI Bilateral and Multilateral Agreements: Europe and Third Countries

Reasons	Total	Europe	Third Countries
Gender diversity is a top priority in the global research landscape	40,69%	35.71%	45.28%
Top organizations are increasingly looking to advance gender equality	18,63%	19.39%	18.87%
To be in alignment with gender equality strategies in the European Union and third countries	25,49%	31.63%	20.75%
To further the inclusion of the gender dimension in research and innovation programs	50,00%	47.96%	51.89%
To meet UN Sustainable Development Goal 5 (Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls)	33,82%	31.63%	35.85%
Demonstrated trends and good practices on the presence of women in decision-making	40,69%	38.78%	42.45%
Economic benefits and the availability of the best human capital	43,63%	43.88%	43.4%
Increased awareness of the benefits of gender sensitive and responsive research	42,65%	46.94%	38.68%
Other	3,43%	4.08%	2.83%
Total	100% (204)	100% (98)	100% (106)

Results for Europe and Third Countries related to the gender perspective are presented in a series of graphs in Annex 6.

3.4.2 Barriers

On a similar note, identifying barriers is one of the survey’s most important questions because perceived barriers allow the project to develop recommendations to address them and engage key stakeholder groups on this issue. This was also a ranking question.

Respondents said that the three main barriers preventing the inclusion of gender equality in STI bilateral and multilateral agreements were: “Underrepresentation of women in decision-making positions” (61.76%); “Stereotypes and unconscious bias” (57.84%); and “Cultural and societal barriers” (57.35%).

Figure 14: Main Barriers or Reasons Preventing the Inclusion of Gender Equality in STI Bilateral and Multilateral Agreements

Breakdown Between Europe and Third Countries

The analysis of the three most popular answers from European and Third Countries participants show that there were not many differences on this issue.

Similarities

Respondents from both groups coincided on all of the barriers preventing the inclusion of gender equality in STI bilateral and multilateral agreements.

Overall, 63.27% of Europeans selected “Stereotypes and unconscious bias” as one of the main barriers, making it the most popular answer. On the other side, 66.04% of respondents from Third Countries chose “Underrepresentation of women in decision-making positions” as one of the main barriers, which was the most selected choice among that group.

European respondents and respondents from Third Countries coincided on the second most selected reason: “Cultural and societal barriers.” That was selected by 60.20% of Europeans and by 55.66% of respondents from Third Countries.

Differences

The groups diverged again on the third most selected barrier. 57.14% of Europeans considered “Underrepresentation of women in decision-making positions” to be an important barrier. Meanwhile, 52.83% of respondents from Third Countries selected “Stereotypes and unconscious bias,” which was the third most selected barrier for that group.

Table 10: Side by Side Comparison of the Main Barriers Preventing the Inclusion of Gender Equality in STI Bilateral and Multilateral Agreements: Europe and Third Countries

Reasons	Total	Europe	Third Countries
Underrepresentation of women in decision-making positions	61,76%	57.14%	66.04%
Stereotypes and unconscious bias	57,84%	63.27%	52.83%
Continued widening of the economic gender gap	14,22%	11.22%	16.98%
Lack of a supportive environment for women in STI	35,29%	35.71%	35.85%
Cultural and societal barriers	57,35%	60.2%	55.66%
Legal barriers	3,43%	2.04%	4.72%
Negotiation power	16,18%	17.35%	15.09%
Lack of belief that gender inequality exists in the research/teams	48,04%	47.96%	48.11%
Other	4,90%	5.1%	4.72%
Total	100% (204)	100% (98)	100% (106)

Results for Europe and Third Countries related to the main barriers or reasons preventing the inclusion of gender equality in agreements are presented in a series of graphs in Annex 7.

Findings on Motivations and Barriers

- Overall, respondents said that the three most important reasons to consider the gender perspective are the following: "To further the inclusion of the gender dimension in research and innovation programs" (50%); "Economic benefits and the availability of the best human capital" (43.63%); and "Increased awareness of the benefits of gender sensitive and responsive research" (42.65%).
- There were not many differences between respondents from Europe and Third Countries regarding the reasons to include the gender perspective in STI agreements.
- Nonetheless, respondents from both groups differed on the second most selected reason. 46.94% of Europeans stated that "Increased awareness of the benefits of gender sensitive and responsive research" was an important reason. On the other side, 45.28% of respondents from Third Countries considered "Gender diversity is a top priority in the global research landscape" to be important.
- Respondents from both groups coincided on all of the barriers preventing the inclusion of gender equality in STI bilateral and multilateral agreements. They are the following: "Underrepresentation of women in decision-making positions"; "Stereotypes and unconscious bias"; and "Cultural and societal barriers".

3.5 Measures to advance the integration of the gender perspective in STI

Finally, we ended our survey on a forward-looking note by asking participants to rank the importance of certain measures to improve gender equality in STI cooperation with other countries, which are presented in the table below.

Overall, the great majority of respondents (more than 82%) believed all the measures included were either “important” or “very important.”

Table 11: Measures to Improve Gender Equality in STI Cooperation with Other Countries

Measures	Not Important	Somewhat Important	Important	Very Important	Total
Include gender equality considerations in the renewal of bilateral and multilateral agreements and/or in future agreements.	1.01%	12.63%	35.86%	50.51%	100% (198)
Develop a gender mainstreaming strategy for STI cooperation with other countries.	2.05%	12.82%	36.41%	48.72%	100% 195
Provide incentives to improve gender equality in STI cooperation with other countries.	1.52%	15.15%	37.88%	45.45%	100% 198
Promote best practices for the involvement of women in the negotiation process of STI agreements with other countries.	2.04%	12.76%	40.82%	44.39%	100% 196
Include an ongoing gender analysis to monitor the integration of the gender dimension into international cooperation STI agreements.	2.02%	15.15%	39.39%	43.43%	100% 198
Conduct impact assessments on all agreements related to STI to ensure that they benefit both men and women equally.	1.53%	16.84%	39.8%	41.84%	100% 196
Support staff training on gender analyses in order to produce gender-sensitive STI agreements, programming and impact evaluations.	3.05%	11.17%	38.07%	47.72%	100% 197
Increase men’s engagement in gender mainstreaming in STI international cooperation.	1.53%	14.8%	35.2%	48.47%	100% 196

Breakdown Between Europe and Third Countries

Comparing responses between respondents from Europe and Third Countries was especially challenging for this question because there weren’t considerable differences. The great majority of respondents from both groups (between 75.27% and 88.35%) considered that all of the measures presented were either “Important” or “Very Important.” On one hand, this is a good sign, as this classification gives the project an idea of proposals that stakeholders on an international level would accept, thereby creating a common starting point for current and future STI cooperation agreements. Nonetheless, it also means that highlighting a specific set of measures is difficult.

Due to the strong consensus presented, we decided to focus on measures where the differences between Europe and Third Countries were within 2 percentage points of each other. Overall, there were only three measures where respondents from Europe and Third Countries coincided in their answers according to this classification:

- **Include gender equality considerations in the renewal of bilateral and multilateral agreements and/or in future agreements.**
 - Europe: 86.32% of respondents said this was “Important” or “Very Important.”
 - Third Countries: 86.41% of respondents this was “Important” or “Very Important.”
 - Difference: 0.09%.
- **Develop a gender mainstreaming strategy for STI cooperation with other countries.**
 - Europe: 84.61% of respondents said this was “Important” or “Very Important.”
 - Third Countries: 85.58% of respondents said this was “Important” or “Very Important.”
 - Difference: 0.97%.
- **Support staff training on gender analyses in order to produce gender-sensitive STI agreements, programming and impact evaluations.**
 - Europe: 84.95% of respondents said this was “Important” or “Very Important.”
 - Third Countries: 86.54% of respondents said this was “Important” or “Very Important.”
 - Difference: 1.59%.

On a similar note, although all measures were considered “Important” or “Very Important” by more than 75% of participants, there were notable differences between both groups in three instances. In this case, we classify a “notable difference” as a difference of more than 5 percentage points.

- **Promote best practices for the involvement of women in the negotiation process of STI agreements with other countries.**
 - Europe: 81.72% of respondents considered this measure “Important” or “Very Important.”
 - Third Countries: 88.35% of respondents considered this measure “Important” or “Very Important.”
 - Difference: 6.63%.
- **Include an ongoing gender analysis to monitor the integration of the gender dimension into international cooperation STI agreements.**
 - Europe: 79.79% of respondents considered this measure “Important” or “Very Important.”
 - Third Countries: 85.58% of respondents considered this measure “Important” or “Very Important.”
 - Difference: 5.79%.
- **Conduct impact assessments on all agreements related to STI to ensure that they benefit both men and women equally.**
 - Europe: 75.27% of respondents considered this measure “Important” or “Very Important.”
 - Third Countries: 87.38% of respondents considered this measure “Important or “Very Important.”
 - Difference: 12.11%.

You can check out the breakdown between groups in the table below.

Table 12: Side by Side Comparison of Measures to Improve Gender Equality in STI Cooperation with Other Countries: Europe and Third Countries

	Measures	Not Important	Somewhat Important	Important	Very Important	Total
Europe	Include gender equality considerations in the renewal of bilateral and multilateral agreements and/or in future agreements.	1.05%	12.63%	47.37%	38.95%	100% (96/98)
Third Countries		0.97%	12.62%	25.24%	61.17%	100% (103/105)
Europe	Develop a gender mainstreaming strategy for STI cooperation with other countries.	1.10%	14.29%	38.46%	46.15%	100% (91/96)
Third Countries		2.88%	11.54%	34.62%	50.96%	100% (104/105)
Europe	Provide incentives to improve gender equality in STI cooperation with other countries.	1.06%	18.09%	42.55%	38.30%	100% (94/96)
Third Countries		1.92%	12.5%	33.65%	51.92%	100% (104/106)
Europe	Promote best practices for the involvement of women in the negotiation process of STI agreements with other countries.	2.15%	16.13%	39.78%	41.94%	100% (93/98)
Third Countries		1.94%	9.71%	41.75%	46.60%	100% (103/106)
Europe	Include an ongoing gender analysis to monitor the integration of the gender dimension into international cooperation STI agreements.	1.06%	19.15%	40.43%	39.36%	100% (94/98)
Third Countries		2.88%	11.54%	38.46%	47.12%	100% (104/106)
Europe	Conduct impact assessments on all agreements related to STI to ensure that they benefit both men and women equally.	2.15%	22.58%	43.01%	32.26%	100% (93/98)
Third Countries		0.97%	11.65%	36.89%	50.49%	100% (103/106)
Europe	Support staff training on gender analyses in order to produce gender-sensitive STI agreements, programming and impact evaluations.	2.15%	12.90%	40.86%	44.09%	100% (93/98)
Third Countries		3.85%	9.62%	35.58%	50.96%	100% (104/106)
Europe	Increase men's engagement in gender mainstreaming in STI international cooperation.	2.17%	13.04%	36.96%	47.83%	100% (92/98)
Third Countries		0.96%	16.35%	33.65%	49.04%	100% (104/106)

Findings on Measures to Improve Gender Equality

- More than 82% of respondents believed all the measures included in the survey were either "Important" or "Very Important."
- When comparing responses from Europe and Third Countries, between 75.27% and 88.35% of respondents from both groups believed all of the measures presented were "Important" or "Very Important."
- Both groups strongly indicated the relevance of the following measures: "Include gender equality considerations in the renewal of bilateral and multilateral agreements and/or in future agreements"; "Develop a gender mainstreaming strategy for STI cooperation with other countries"; and "Support staff training on gender analyses in order to produce gender-sensitive STI agreements, programming and impact evaluations".
- However, respondents from Europe and Third Countries didn't always agree on the importance of certain measures. The following three measures were considered more relevant for respondents from Third Countries: "Conduct impact assessments on all agreements related to STI to ensure that they benefit both men and women equally"; "Promote best practices for the involvement of women in the negotiation process of STI agreements with other countries" and "Include an ongoing gender analysis to monitor the integration of the gender dimension into international cooperation STI agreements".

3.6 Insights From Respondents

In the final section of the survey, participants were asked to provide comments on a voluntary basis regarding gender in STI or the questionnaire. Overall, 39 individuals left comments (19.11%), the majority of which were very detailed. All of the comments can be found in Annex 8.

Although respondents discussed a number of issues in their comments, there were some themes we found particularly meaningful and worth highlighting. They are as follows:

- **There is a lack of information available to researchers about STI bilateral and multilateral agreements. This theme was also reflected in data collected by the survey.**
 - Comment from survey respondent: *"My university is large, and I do not know about the various agreements"*.
 - Comment from survey respondent: *"Although I am currently head of [my] department, I do not have access to the bilateral or international agreements signed by my organization, thus, I did not know many answers to previous questions."*
 - Comment from survey respondent: *"There is a lack of information towards researchers regarding the STI cooperation agreements in my organization"*.

- **Women are provided different opportunities in STI depending on what country they work in.**
 - Comment from survey respondent: *"Since I am social scientist, I can tell from my experience that the entire system of formal and informal jobs in India are highly biased against women. It is so obvious at the top level decision making and exists in subtle ways at lower levels of hierarchy. Moreover, cultural and social biases in the family and society, and insensitivity of men towards women and her work are further aspects that need to be addressed."*
 - Comment from survey respondent: *"It is important to understand the different conditions for women depending on the social and economic context. In the global south there are no conditions to participate equally in the decision-making process or to contribute equally in producing STI."*
- **Career opportunities and advancement is an important factor for achieving gender equality in STI.**
 - Comment from survey respondent: *"For institutionalization of gender equal practices in Science, Technology and Innovation, we need to tackle the inequalities in hiring, compensation, development, representation and leadership opportunities of women across all research projects, committees and panels. This should be supported by policies and enablers that help women meet their work commitments effectively and prevent them from falling off the workforce."*
 - Comment from survey respondent: *"To increase participation of women in STI and to remove barriers, it is important to engage institutions and to develop policies related to eliminating biases and to provide incentives that promote the advancement of women. Recruiting is important but promotion and career advancement is even more important. Changes must [happen] at the institutional level to make a difference."*
- **There should be equal opportunities for all, regardless of their gender.**
 - Comment from survey respondent: *"I think that opportunities must be the same for a person, independently of the gender. All positions must be given to the best person in the room according to personal knowledge, abilities, etc. in terms of the position's profile to be covered"*
 - Comment from survey respondent: *"Establish clear criteria of knowledge to access a negotiation position, research, ... based on the appropriate training for them and when accessing with the anonymous CV. In this way the best will be selected and I am sure there will be enough women."*

4 CONCLUSION

Survey results suggest that there is a lot of common ground between Europe and Third Countries on what needs to be done to include and improve gender equality provisions in bilateral and multilateral agreements in STI between regions. When breaking out results from Europeans and respondents from Third Countries, we do see some differences, which suggests that different regions have different priority issues regarding the implementation of gender equality, which should be considered when negotiating bilateral and multilateral agreements in STI.

While the insights gained from the survey are welcome, it is important to acknowledge its limitations. Due to the breadth of issues covered in the survey, some respondents said they felt they could not answer many questions. Others also said the scope of the survey made them unsure as to whether they were the correct target group, which suggests that we could have made our survey description clearer. Additionally, many of the questions regarding the most important issues or measures related to, for example, gender equality in scientific careers were not weighted. Although this allowed us to obtain an idea of what issues were important, it did not allow us to determine which issues were a priority.

Nonetheless, the results of the survey provide valuable evidence for the Gender STI project, which seeks to analyze and promote gender equality in bilateral and multilateral STI agreements. They will be a key asset for when the project develops recommendations to improve gender equality in these agreements.

ANNEX 1 - QUESTIONNAIRE

1. What country is your organization located in?

2. What is your gender?

- Woman
- Man
- Nonbinary

3. What region do you live in?

- Europe
- Third Countries
- N/A

4. How would you describe your organization? Please select all that apply.

- Government organization
- Funding organization
- Research and Technology Organization (RTO)
- University
- Foundation
- Private company
- Public company
- STI agency/association
- Non-governmental organization (NGO)
- Other (please specify)

5. What is your current position in your organization?

- Government official/civil servant
- Funding agency representative
- Director
- Head of Department
- Project Manager
- Researcher
- Professor
- Other (please specify)

6. Has **your organization** formed STI cooperation agreements with other countries?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

7. Has **your organization** included gender related provisions in ongoing STI cooperation agreements, such as those included below, with other countries over the last five years?

	Always	Sometimes	Never	I don't know	Not Applicable
Bilateral Agreement	<input type="radio"/>				
Multilateral Agreement	<input type="radio"/>				
Bilateral Memorandum of Understanding (MoU)	<input type="radio"/>				
Multilateral Memorandum of Understanding (MoU)	<input type="radio"/>				
STI implementation activities (e.g., call for proposals, rules for participation, evaluation criteria, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>				

Other (please specify)

8. If **your organization** considered gender related provisions in any way in ongoing STI cooperation agreements, please indicate in what areas gender equality aspects are addressed in the agreements. Select all that apply.

	Always	Sometimes	Never	I don't know	Not Applicable
Agreements advice/recommendations on implementing gender equality	<input type="radio"/>				
STI objectives/priorities (e.g., strengthen research excellence, increase the number of women researchers in STI activities, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>				
Evaluation criteria for STI programs/projects	<input type="radio"/>				
Monitoring of STI programs/projects	<input type="radio"/>				
Calls for proposals/applications	<input type="radio"/>				
Rules for participation	<input type="radio"/>				
Impact of project results	<input type="radio"/>				
Science communication	<input type="radio"/>				
Contribution to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)	<input type="radio"/>				
Gender dimension in research content	<input type="radio"/>				

Other (please specify)

9. Does **your organization** consider addressing gender equality when it renews or establishes new STI agreements with other countries?

	Always	Sometimes	Never	I don't know	Not Applicable
Bilateral Agreements	<input type="radio"/>				
Multilateral Agreements	<input type="radio"/>				
Bilateral Memorandum of Understanding (MoU)	<input type="radio"/>				
Multilateral Memorandum of Understanding (MoU)	<input type="radio"/>				
STI implementation activities (e.g., call for proposals, rules for participation, evaluation criteria, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>				

Other (please specify)

10. If **your organization** is considering addressing gender equality when it renews or establishes new STI agreements with other countries, please indicate in what areas gender equality aspects will be considered in the agreements. Select all that apply.

	Always	Sometimes	Never	I don't know	Not Applicable
Advice/recommendations on implementing gender equality	<input type="radio"/>				
STI objectives/priorities (e.g., strengthen research excellence, increase the number of women researchers in STI activities, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>				
Evaluation criteria for STI programs/projects	<input type="radio"/>				
Monitoring of STI programs/projects	<input type="radio"/>				
Calls for proposals/applications	<input type="radio"/>				
Rules for participation	<input type="radio"/>				
Impact of project results	<input type="radio"/>				
Science communication	<input type="radio"/>				
Contribution to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)	<input type="radio"/>				
Gender dimension in research content	<input type="radio"/>				

Other (please specify)

* 11. From an international cooperation perspective, please rank the following approaches to improve **gender equality in STI when it comes to scientific careers** at all levels.

Please select the **three most important**.

- Gender equality in recruitment and career progression
- Inclusive language for job vacancies
- Parental leave policies/flexible work schedule arrangements
- Job security for women in the long-term
- Visibility to women references in science
- Training on equitable hiring practices
- Mentorship of women by other women
- Incentives for women to lead projects
- Gender balanced peer reviews
- Retaining women scientists (i.e., leaking pipeline)
- Unconscious bias training for the scientific community
- Other (please specify)

* 12. From an international cooperation perspective, what do you consider needs to be addressed to improve the **gender balance in decision-making bodies and positions in STI**?

Please select the **three most important**.

- Gender balance in STI policy dialogues
- Participation of women in the negotiation of STI agreements
- Introducing gender quotas for evaluation panels to ensure a gender-balanced composition
- Disseminating updated information, trends and good practices on gender equality in decision-making
- Policies to increase the proportion of women in STI
- Ensuring transparent nomination and promotion schemes in political and corporate cultures
- Unconscious bias training on gender balance in leadership positions
- Other (please specify)

* 13. From an international cooperation perspective, what do you consider needs to be addressed to integrate the **gender dimension in research and innovation content**?

Please select the **three most important**.

- Consider gender in the entire research and innovation process
- Address gender bias in research design
- Ensure gender balance in evaluation panels
- Ensure gender balance in research teams
- Include gender factors in application forms
- Create criteria to monitor the gender dimension in research content, processes and outcomes
- Other (please specify)

* 14. Why do you think the gender perspective should be included in STI bilateral and multilateral agreements (formal and informal)?

Please select the **three most important reasons**.

- Gender diversity is a top priority in the global research landscape
- Top organizations are increasingly looking to advance gender equality
- To be in alignment with gender equality strategies in the European Union and third countries
- To further the inclusion of the gender dimension in research and innovation programs
- To meet UN Sustainable Development Goal 5 (Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls)
- Demonstrated trends and good practices on the presence of women in decision-making
- Economic benefits and the availability of the best human capital
- Increased awareness of the benefits of gender sensitive and responsive research
- Other (please specify)

* 15. What do you think are the main barriers or reasons preventing the inclusion of gender equality in STI bilateral and multilateral agreements (formal and/or informal)?

Please select the **three most important barriers or reasons**.

- Underrepresentation of women in decision-making positions
- Stereotypes and unconscious bias
- Continued widening of the economic gender gap
- Lack of a supportive environment for women in STI
- Cultural and societal barriers
- Legal barriers
- Negotiation power
- Lack of belief that gender inequality exists in the research/teams
- Other (please specify)

16. In your opinion, how important are the following measures to improve gender equality in STI cooperation with other countries? Please rate them from 1 (not important) to 4 (very important).

	1 - Not important	2 - Somewhat important	3 - Important	4 - Very Important
Include gender equality considerations in the renewal of bilateral and multilateral agreements and/or in future agreements.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Develop a gender mainstreaming strategy for STI cooperation with other countries.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Provide incentives to improve gender equality in STI cooperation with other countries.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Promote best practices for the involvement of women in the negotiation process of STI agreements with other countries.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Include an ongoing gender analysis to monitor the integration of the gender dimension into international cooperation STI agreements.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Conduct impact assessments on all agreements related to STI to ensure that they benefit both men and women equally.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Support staff training on gender analyses in order to produce gender-sensitive STI agreements, programming and impact evaluations.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Increase men's engagement in gender mainstreaming in STI international cooperation.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Other (please specify)

17. If you have other comments regarding gender in STI or this survey, please share them here.

18. If you would like to receive the results of the survey, please include your email below.

Done

ANNEX 2 – EXAMPLES OF COMMUNICATION ACTIONS TO PROMOTE THE SURVEY

Survey Blog

NEWS
14.06.2021

The GENDER STI project on Monday launched a survey that aims to assess the current state of gender equality in international cooperation in science, technology and innovation (STI). Specifically, the survey will analyze gender equality in bilateral and multilateral agreements between European Member States, Associated Countries and selected third countries.

The “Survey on Gender Equality in STI Bilateral and Multilateral Agreements” will be sent out to identified key actors—ranging from government organizations, funding organizations, universities and more—across European countries and 10 selected third countries. It will inquire about their perceptions on the implementation of gender equality in these agreements, which include bilateral agreements, multilateral agreements and memorandums of understanding, among others.

The questionnaire will also seek to study whether gender equality is considered in STI implementation activities, such as calls for proposals, rules for participation and evaluation criteria.

Survey Blog Full Text

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The questionnaire will also seek to study whether gender equality is considered in STI implementation activities, such as calls for proposals, rules for participation and evaluation criteria.

Importantly, the survey will attempt to identify the main barriers or reasons that prevent the inclusion of gender equality in STI bilateral and multilateral agreements.

European actors consider gender equality in STI to be a strategic issue in policy dialogues with third countries. In recent years, the [Council of the European Union](#) has invited the European Commission and Member States to consider including a gender perspective in dialogues with third countries in STI.

In addition, the survey seeks to collect valuable input on key measures to address this important issue across three objectives: gender equality in scientific careers, gender balance in decision-making bodies and the gender dimension in research and

innovation content. These three objectives are part of the European Commission's [strategy for gender equality](#) within the European Research Area.

Survey results will ultimately contribute to Gender STI's mapping of gender equality in STI bilateral and multilateral agreements. The mapping will be used to develop an action plan for recommendations on the integration of gender equality in STI dialogues.

Link: <https://www.gender-sti.org/survey-gender-equality-sti-international-agreements/>

Twitter Post

Facebook Post

LinkedIn Post

Survey Email Campaign

SURVEY ON
Gender Equality in
STI Bilateral and
Multilateral Agreements

Gender STI **2021**

Dear *|FNAME|*,

I hope this email finds you well. I'm writing to invite you to participate in the Gender STI Project's "Survey on Gender Equality in Bilateral and Multilateral Agreements." [Gender STI](#) is our newest Horizon 2020 research project that aims to analyze gender equality in international cooperation.

The survey is part of Gender STI's research activities and results from it will contribute to the project's mapping on gender equality in bilateral and multilateral agreements between Europe and third countries. In addition, the mapping will be used to develop recommendations on the integration of gender equality in STI dialogues.

July
31

Take the Gender STI survey by July 31!

TAKE SURVEY

Note: Apologies if you receive this invitation more than once.

ANNEX 3 – GRAPHICAL COMPARISON OF APPROACHES TO IMPROVE GENDER EQUALITY IN STI IN SCIENTIFIC CAREERS

Europe

Third Countries

ANNEX 4 – GRAPHICAL COMPARISON OF ISSUES TO ADDRESS TO IMPROVE THE GENDER BALANCE IN DECISION-MAKING BODIES AND POSITIONS IN STI

Europe

Third Countries

ANNEX 5 – GRAPHICAL COMPARISON OF ISSUES TO ADDRESS TO INTEGRATE THE GENDER DIMENSION IN RESEARCH AND INNOVATION CONTENT

Europe

Third Countries

ANNEX 6 – GRAPHICAL COMPARISON OF REASONS WHY THE GENDER PERSPECTIVE SHOULD BE INCLUDED IN STI AGREEMENTS

Europe

Third Countries

ANNEX 7 – GRAPHICAL COMPARISON OF THE MAIN BARRIERS PREVENTING THE INCLUSION OF GENDER EQUALITY IN STI AGREEMENTS

Europe

Third Countries

ANNEX 8 – COMMENTS FROM SURVEY RESPONDENTS

- It was not always clear, if you wanted to have strictly the organisation's views or personal views of the responding person. Question 10: the wording of alternative 5. is a bit strange; we take it to mean that it is important to give visibility to female researchers. It should be possible to select 0-3 alternatives instead of fixed 3.
- It would have been important to outline to whom this survey is aimed for. Now the aim remained unclear.
- My university is large, and I do not know about the various agreements (ie. questions 7-9)
- I found some of the "choose three" alternatives ambiguous. For example, inclusive language for job vacancies and training in equitable hiring practices are both parts of gender equality in recruitment and career progression (this is just one example, there are others). How could I tick training in equitable hiring practices but not tick gender equality in recruitment and career progression? For me it was also unclear if you with STI agreements mean agreements where all the three elements are explicitly mentioned, or if science (=research) or science and technology agreements are also eligible, so that is why you did not get any reply in the first part of the questionnaire.
- Men need to be part of every step, too. Gender equity cannot be achieved if only women are involved in the processes.
- At this point, I would not exclude agreements with partners that would not agree to our rules regarding gender equality.
- Since I am social scientist I can tell from my experience that the entire system of formal and informal jobs in India are highly biased against women. It is so obvious at the top level decision making and exists in subtle ways at lower levels of hierarchy. Moreover, cultural and social biases in the family and society, and insensitivity of men towards women and her work are further aspects that need to be addressed.
- It is important to understand the different conditions for women depending on the social and economic context. In the global south there are no conditions to participate equally in the decision-making process or to contribute equally in producing STI.
- For institutionalization of gender equal practices in Science, Technology and Innovation, we need to tackle the inequalities in hiring, compensation, development, representation and leadership opportunities of women across all research projects, committees and panels. This should be supported by policies and enablers that help women meet their work commitments effectively and prevent them from falling off the workforce.
- Gender training and analysis is a must for transformation of gender relations. Mere presence of women will not ensure change or gender equality, what is required is awareness generation, power analysis and most important integrating an intersectional analysis of class, race, caste, religion, ethnicity

and other socio-economic stratifications which create disempowering conditions for specific women

- All the above answers apply to university agreements or MoUs.
- In my institution, the gender issue has been “instilled and implemented” in the last 4 years. There is a Gender and Diversity Department that addresses this issue and promotes the participation of female workers and students.

It is necessary to incorporate concrete conditions in agreements with other institutions, especially from other countries and not only related to Science, Technology and Innovation (STI) but also in art, law and recreation as well.

- In my view, efforts for gender equality must somehow ensure academic and research excellence.

It is important to provide opportunities for women to always stand out for their qualities in science and research.

- If 51% of the world population are women, it’s a fact that they have to be included to improve positive results in any task.
- I think that opportunities must be the same for a person, independently of the gender. All positions must be given to the best person in the room according to personal knowledge, abilities, etc. in terms of the position's profile to be covered.
- Universities must address efforts in order to:

-Design and apply gender equity measurement instruments that allow describing and analyzing the situation of the University in the matter;

-Encourage the inclusion of information on gender equality in induction courses and welcome activities for new students, as well as in tutoring programs;

-Promote before the competent authorities the review of study plans and programs to include the gender perspective;

-Collaborate in the creation and dissemination of teaching materials with a gender perspective;

-Promote the dissemination and implementation of continuing education activities related to gender equality, for the university community and the general public, as a core aspect for progress towards gender equality at universities.

- Gender issue has to do with cultural and bias aspects, we need to improve the first and get rid of the second. The final target must be to obtain from a mixed pool the best selection rather than going for a poor team but gender balanced.
- Although I am currently head of department, I do not have access to the bilateral or international agreements signed by my organization, thus, I did not know many answers to previous questions.

- Thank you for the opportunity to complete this survey. It is valuable to raise these questions related to bilateral and multilateral agreements. At our agency the focus is more on equity, diversity and inclusion, rather than gender, and when we do focus on gender we generally seek information on diverse genders, so while we have responded to the gender-focused questions, this may not capture the full picture.

In some cases the questions were not easy to respond to due to different uses of terminology and concepts. For example, question 10 refers to "gender equality in STI careers." We were unclear as to if gender equality refers here to equity, as in equitable representation, participation, status and decision-making of (diverse) genders?

- Excellent initiative. Congratulations.
- La temática referida al género debe ser una política de todos los Estados, a nivel interno y en lo referido a la articulación a través de los Convenios Internacionales.
- There is a lack of information towards researchers regarding the STI cooperation agreements in my organization.
- It would be relevant to consider the barriers to women long-lasting involvement in STI (including leadership positions) taking into account both women with children/families and single women so as to accurately identify all gender-related bottlenecks.
- As stated before, in my field of computing engineering the main origin of gender inequality is the unreasonable absence of women in the field, having been proved their successful performance if they get involved.
- To increase participation of women in STI and to remove barriers, it is important to engage institutions and to develop policies related to eliminating biases and to provide incentives that promote the advancement of women. Recruiting is important but promotion and career advancement is even more important. Changes must happen at the institutional level to make a difference.
- It is important to discuss how to improve evaluation with a gender perspective.
- Survey is good.
- There is emerging gender sensitivity with researches, but often does not culminate into action. The gap between thought and action needs to be bridged with continuous orientation, capacity building, training etc. to both men and women and exposing to the fruits of ensuring gender equality.
- Women must be part of policy framing, designing project, inline ration and beneficiary of all STI related activities research and plans.
- Sometimes we get better results by including specific aspects or gender considerations in calls for proposals and other mechanisms or project rules than negotiating specific gender clauses in international agreements due to some local barriers.

- Establish clear criteria of knowledge to access a negotiation position, research, ... based on the appropriate training for them and when accessing with the anonymous CV. In this way the best will be selected and I am sure there will be enough women.
- The only way to address this problem is through "positive discrimination" policies that force the inclusion of gender in every project or program that is developed.

For the next generation, it will be a solved problem.

- An assessment of gender understanding of men and women in STI will help in recognising factors impeding the improvement of gender sensitive STI processes.
- I think there is one very important issue that was not mentioned earlier: to ensure safe space for women/men/non-binary people in terms of sexual harassment.
- Including gender issues must be a women and men's work together.
- Both companies and governments have realized that without the inclusion of the expertise and experience of women, representing more than 50 percent of the world's population, in STI and STEM overall economic and social benefits of any funded project are woefully curtailed.
- I wasn't confident that I understood what was meant by "Increase men's engagement in gender mainstreaming in STI international cooperation. "
- This is a great project and effort. We need to get more countries' top policy makers involved.
- Focus should be on demonstrating and communicating the disadvantages of non-diverse perspectives, and incentivizing research impacts that reflect the benefits of gender-diverse teams.